

IMPACT OF ANDON-BASED VISUAL CONTROL ON NON-VALUE-ADDED TIME

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Abstract—This paper applies Andon-based visual control to reduce non-value-added activities in Bangladesh’s footwear industry. Using time study, VSM, root cause analysis and PDCA, the study reduced NVA time from 47.68% to 22.90% and total production time from 968.75 s to 806.25 s. Line efficiency improved by 16.77% without major capital investment. The results show that Andon-based visual control can reduce waste and improve production efficiency.

Keywords— Lean manufacturing, Andon system, Non-value-added time, Footwear industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lean manufacturing reduces non-value-added work and improves productivity in manufacturing systems [1]. In footwear production, excess movement, waiting, rework and WIP can reduce line efficiency.

Process mapping and integrated lean tools help identify bottlenecks and reduce waste [2]. This study applies time study, VSM, root cause analysis, PDCA and Andon-based visual control to improve footwear line efficiency.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study used a single-factory case study approach based on direct observation, stopwatch time study and production record review.

A. Lean Tools Used

Value stream mapping, root cause analysis, seven wastes analysis, bottleneck analysis and PDCA were used to identify waste and develop improvement actions.

B. Andon-Based Improvement

An Andon-based visual control system was introduced to reduce unnecessary worker movement and improve communication during defect handling.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The baseline study identified excess movement, waiting and rework as major NVA sources. After Andon-based visual control was implemented, problem communication became faster, reducing unnecessary movement and improving workflow stability.

Total production time decreased from 968.75 s to 806.25 s, and NVA time decreased from 312.75 s to 150.25 s. The NVA percentage dropped from 47.68% to 22.90%, while line efficiency improved by 16.77% without major capital investment. Table 1 summarizes the before-and-after performance comparison, including total production time, NVA time, NVA percentage and line efficiency after Andon implementation.

Table 1. Performance summary before and after Andon implementation.

Parameter	Before Andon	After Andon	Improvement
Total Production Time (s)	968.75	806.25	-16.77%
NVA Time (s)	312.75	150.25	-51.96%
NVA Percentage (%)	47.68	22.90	-24.78
Line Efficiency (%)	52.32	69.09	+16.77%

Figure 1. Comparison of production performance before and after Andon implementation.

Figure 1 compares total production time, NVA time and NVA percentage before and after Andon implementation, demonstrating reduced waste and improved workflow efficiency.

IV. CONCLUSION

Andon-based visual control reduced NVA time from 47.68% to 22.90% and improved line efficiency by 16.77% without major capital investment. Future work should test this approach across more production lines.

References

- [1] A. Palange and P. Dhattrak, “Lean manufacturing a vital tool to enhance productivity in manufacturing,” *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 46, pp. 729–736, 2021.
- [2] K. Kumar, D. Dhingra, and B. Singh, “Lean-Kaizen implementation: A roadmap for identifying continuous improvement opportunities in Indian small and medium sized enterprise,” *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 2018.